

ADVANCING THE LEGAL REVIEW OF AUTONOMOUS WEAPON SYSTEMS

REPORT OF AN EXPERT MEETING
(SYDNEY, 16–18 APRIL 2024)

Renato Wolf
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Contents

Acknowledgments and disclaimer	iv
Contributors	v
Abbreviations	vii
Executive summary	viii
Foreword	x
1 Introduction	2
1.1 Organisation of the Expert Meeting	2
1.2 Content and objectives of the Report	3
2 Ongoing international discussions	4
2.1 Group of Governmental Experts	4
2.2 United Nations General Assembly	5
3 Developments in legal review practice	7
3.1 Australia	7
3.2 New Zealand	8
3.3 Singapore	9
3.4 Sweden	9
3.5 Switzerland	10
3.6 United Kingdom	11
3.7 United States	12
3.8 International Committee of the Red Cross	13
4 Thematic overview of workshop discussions	16
4.1 Locating legal reviews	16
4.2 Lexicon	16
4.3 Legal reviews of weapons/means and legal reviews of methods	17
4.4 Legal review as process versus outcome	17
4.5 Multidisciplinary approach	18
4.6 Security of autonomous weapon systems	18
4.7 Role of industry	18
4.8 Information-sharing and transparency	19
5 Conclusion	20
Annexes	22
A Elements of good practice	22
B Scenarios	30
C Participants	33
D Resources	35

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The views and opinions expressed in this report are those of the authors, and do not necessarily reflect the views of the Australian Government or any other government or organisation whose representatives participated in their personal capacities in the Expert Meeting.

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Abbreviations

AI	artificial intelligence
AP I	Protocol (I) Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts
AWS	autonomous weapon system(s)
CCW	Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects
GGE	Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems
HCP	High Contracting Parties
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IHL	international humanitarian law
LAWS	lethal autonomous weapon system(s)
MHCP	Meeting of High Contracting Parties
REAIM	Responsible AI in the Military Domain Summit
TEVV	testing, evaluation, verification, and validation
TTPs	tactics, techniques and procedures
UK	United Kingdom
US	United States

Executive summary

This Report provides a summary of an expert meeting on the legal review of autonomous weapons systems ('AWS'), which was convened by the Directorate of Operations and International Law, Australian Defence Force, in Sydney in April 2024 ('Expert Meeting'), and chaired by Colonel Damian Copeland. This Meeting was the second such meeting, building upon the inaugural Expert Meeting ('First Meeting') which took place in Sydney in March 2023. The Expert Meeting was attended by governmental and non-governmental experts from eight States (Australia, New Zealand, Norway, Singapore, Sweden, Switzerland, the United Kingdom and the United States).

Since the First Meeting, the discussion about the utility of the conduct of legal reviews has intensified in multilateral fora, most notably within the Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems ('GGE'), mandated by the High Contracting Parties ('HCPs') to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects ('CCW'). This enhanced focus has been reflected in academic discourse, and is in part a result of operationalisation by those States that have adopted military technologies that incorporate autonomy. This Meeting provided an opportunity to review the progress of international discourse about the regulation of AWS generally, as well as how legal reviews have featured in that debate. A summary of this update is included in **Part 2** of this report.

This focus of the current international debate aligns with the general rationale for this Expert Meeting. Legal reviews of AWS are a method to assess a State's ability to comply with and implement international law but they can also function as a confidence building measure when States share information about the conduct and process of legal reviews. Accordingly, a stated aim of this Meeting was to enhance State cooperation through the sharing of practices as they relate to the legal review of AWS. This was achieved on the first day of the Meeting, by governmental experts providing updates and further information about their national practices as they pertain to the conduct of legal reviews, and the review of AWS and, autonomous or AI-enabled capabilities more generally (referred to as 'military AI, or 'MAI' hereafter). A summary of these practices is included in **Part 3** of this report.

Separate to enhancing State information sharing in undertaking legal reviews of AWS, this Meeting undertook to again reflect upon the specific practices related to the conduct of legal reviews that may require adjustment to account for the challenges presented by AWS, and the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) and autonomy into military capabilities, more generally. A number of themes emerged from this discussion. They are:

- legal reviews in the context of other processes;

- lexicon with definitions of key terms;
- legal reviews of weapons / means and legal review of methods;
- legal review as a process compared to legal reviews as an outcome;
- multi-disciplinary approach to legal reviews;
- security of AWS;
- the role of industry in the legal review of AWS; and
- information-sharing and transparency in the legal review of AWS.

These themes are addressed in **Part 4** of the Report.

In spite of this invigorated focus on legal reviews, the practice of legal reviews by States, either in satisfaction of their legal obligation under article 36 of Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions ('AP I'), or as a matter of policy, remains far from universal. In addition to the confidence building function undertaken in relation to the sharing of State-specific practices, the second iteration of this meeting has worked to consolidate an international community of practice of like-minded States (and their representatives), and practitioners from industry and academia, who are building the corpus of knowledge about the methods by which the challenges presented by AWS in conducting a sufficiently robust legal reviews, can be overcome. This community of practice has also contributed to discussion and understanding of Elements of Good Practice in the review of AWS, which is addressed separately to this report (see **Part 5**, regarding next steps).

Foreword

The legal review of weapons remains an important legal obligation for many States and a central component of the international debate concerning the regulation of autonomous weapon systems ('AWS'). Irrespective of national positions on the need for new international law, there is a strong consensus on the value of legal reviews as both a legal requirement where applicable and, in all cases, an effective practice to support implementation of international law and a confidence building measure.

The First Expert Meeting on the legal review of AWS, held in Sydney from 28-30 March 2023, was intended to create a mechanism for the voluntary exchange of best practice and identify the elements of such practice. The Meeting provided an invaluable opportunity for participants to discuss current legal review practice and identify challenges that arise in the legal review of AWS. While there were some clear differences, many of the challenges identified were found to be common amongst the participating States. The benefit of the Meeting was clear as a means to promote transparency and information sharing. The Meeting report included a set of elements of best practice intended to assist States to undertake legal reviews of AWS and address the unique challenges presented by autonomy in weapons.

This report on the Second Expert Meeting on the legal review of AWS, held in Sydney from 16-18 April 2024, describes how the Meeting achieved its aim of building upon the outcomes of the First Meeting. In particular, it notes the increased number of States represented at the Meeting and the development of the draft elements of good practice by providing commentary explaining each of the elements. Similar to the 2023 Meeting, participants from States, non-government organisations, academics and industry provided multi-stakeholder input to the discussion which enhanced the clarity and utility of the draft. The participants also considered the benefit of creating an online portal to enable the voluntary exchange of information concerning the legal review obligation generally and its application to specific technologies including AWS.

There remains work to be done in this area. Recognising that not all States undertake legal reviews, I hope this Expert Meeting to become an annual event that allows States, NGOs, academia and industry to contribute to an increase and development of legal review practice by States and understanding of its process and requirements, particularly by those responsible for the research and development of new weapons technologies. I welcome the opportunity for other States to host future events either on an international or regional basis.

I am indebted to the authors of this report for their professionalism and dedication to this project. The report is an important contribution to the international discussion of national practice for the legal review of weapons. I hope it enables ongoing focus on the development and exchange of good practice.

Damian Copeland

Colonel

Director Operations and International Law

Australian Defence Force

1 Introduction

1.1 Organisation of the Expert Meeting

On 16–18 April 2024, the Directorate of Operations and International Law, Australian Defence Force, convened a Second Expert Meeting on the Legal Review of Autonomous Weapon Systems at Victoria Barracks, Sydney ('Expert Meeting'). This Meeting followed the inaugural Expert Meeting, held in Sydney on 28–30 March 2023 ('First Meeting').

The Expert Meeting was chaired by Colonel Damian Copeland. The Meeting was attended by 43 experts from government (including military and civilian personnel responsible for legal reviews), the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), non-governmental organisations, academia and the defence industry. Experts from six States (Australia, Brazil, New Zealand, Sweden, the United Kingdom and the United States) participated in the First Meeting. This Expert Meeting drew participants from three further States (Norway, Singapore and Switzerland), whereas the Brazilian participant who attended the First Meeting was unable to join.

This report seeks to build upon the report that followed this First Meeting.¹ Accordingly, it will not reproduce the background in relation to the genesis of the First Meeting or this Meeting, nor the justification for the focus upon legal reviews of AWS.²

The Expert Meeting had three stated aims:

- to meet as a community of practice;
- to update participants on significant activities that had occurred in the field of legal reviews relevant to AWS since the First Meeting, and to again exchange current State practices and policies relevant to these reviews; and
- to consider and refine the Elements of Good Practice attached as Annex A to the First Meeting Report and reproduced with amendments as **Annex A** to this Report.

The first aim was achieved through the conduct of the Meeting itself. In meeting for a second time, the group of experts (see **Annex C** to this Report) was expanded from those who attended the inaugural Meeting, indicating the value in collaboration and information sharing in this type of forum regarding the challenges associated with the legal review of AWS.

1 Netta Goussac, Natalia Jevglevskaja, Rain Liivoja and Lauren Sanders, *Enhancing the Legal Review of Autonomous Weapon Systems: Report of an Expert Meeting (Sydney, 28–30 March 2023)* (Brisbane: Law and the Future of War Research Group, TC Beirne School of Law, The University of Queensland, May 2023) <doi.org/10.14264/2bbfd31> (hereinafter *Enhancing the Legal Review*).

2 See *ibid* and the Foreword to this Report.

The second objective was achieved through a number of presentations and discussions by experts from government, the ICRC, non-governmental organisations, industry and academia.

The third aim was achieved through discussing each Element of Good Practice. An aide-memoire, explaining the genesis of these Proposed Elements of Good Practice, and the key issues raised in relation to them following input from the First Expert Meeting and associated consultations, was circulated prior to the conduct of the meeting to focus this discussion (see **Annex A** for an abridged version).

1.2 Content and objectives of the Report

This Report seeks to complement and update the report provided at the conclusion of the First Expert Meeting, specifically as it relates to the State practice presented by State representatives, and in respect of an overview of the discussions held during the Meeting and an assessment of the key themes that arose over the course of the Meeting.

This Report is comprised of the below main parts:

- an overview of ongoing international discussions (**Part 2**);
- developments in State practice (**Part 3**);
- themes arising from a discussion of the Elements of Good Practice (**Part 4**); and
- conclusion and next steps (**Part 5**).

The Report has four annexes:

- a draft list of Elements of Good Practices in the Legal Review of AWS and focus questions provided to Meeting participants prior to the Meeting (**Annex A**);
- case scenarios that were utilised to facilitate discussion during certain sessions of the Meeting (**Annex B**);
- a list of meeting participants (**Annex C**); and
- an updated list of resources that may assist the reader (**Annex D**).

As with the report of the First Meeting, this Report contains an independent summary of the discussions of the Expert Meeting. The views expressed in this Report are those of the authors, informed by the discussions at the meeting. While a draft of this Report was circulated among meeting participants, the final Report does not seek to reflect consensus views. Furthermore, the Expert Meeting was held on the understanding that participant interventions would not be attributed to individuals unless they expressly requested attribution or were explicitly representing State positions. Accordingly, this Report does not attribute particular statements to individual participants.

Finally, similar to the outcomes of the First Meeting, this Report is intended to act as a prompt for further discussion and debate about the legal review of AWS. It is clear that there is an emerging international community of practice interested in, and engaged with, the concept of enhancing IHL compliance through the conduct of legal reviews of AWS and military AI more generally. The authors hope that this Report will assist in consolidating this interest and community, to support future and regular exchanges of practices and ideas on this topic.

2 Ongoing international discussions

2.1 Group of Governmental Experts

Discussions about the regulation of AWS have taken place in multilateral fora for over a decade. Following the initial expression of concern by the civil society and the United Nations Special Rapporteur on Extrajudicial, Summary or Arbitrary Executions,³ the Human Rights Council discussed the development of ‘lethal autonomous robots’ in May 2013.⁴ The CCW Meeting of HCPs (‘MHCP’), held in November the same year, welcomed a proposal ‘to explore the questions related to emerging technologies in the area of lethal autonomous weapons systems’ and decided to convene informal meeting of experts in 2014 to discuss these questions;⁵ similar meetings were also convened in 2015 and 2016. The Fifth Review Conference, welcoming these informal discussions, decided to establish a more formal open-ended Group of Governmental Experts (‘GGE’) related to emerging technologies in the area of lethal autonomous weapons systems.⁶ This GGE mandate has been revised and extended by subsequent CCW MHCPs and the Sixth Review Conference, and has consequently met in annual sessions from 2017 onwards.

Over the course of a decade of discussions about AWS under the auspices of the CCW, legal reviews have been mentioned frequently. Thus, during the 2014–2016 informal expert meetings, multiple States made statements and put forward working papers in relation to their national legal review processes. In 2018 and 2019, the GGE adopted a set of guiding principles, which acknowledge the significance of legal reviews by using language mirroring article 36 of AP I:

In accordance with States’ obligations under international law, in the study, development, acquisition, or adoption of a new weapon, means or method of warfare, determination must be made whether its employment would, in some or all circumstances, be prohibited by international law.⁷

3 Christof Heyns, *Report of the Special Rapporteur on Extrajudicial, Summary or Arbitrary Executions* (9 April 2013) [A/HRC/23/47](#).

4 Human Rights Council, *Order of the Day, Thursday, 30 May 2013* (27 May 2013) [A/HRC/23/OD/4](#).

5 *Final Report of the 2013 Meeting of the High Contracting Parties to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects* (16 December 2013) [CCW/MSP/2013/10](#) paras 18 and 32.

6 *Final Document of the Fifth Review Conference of the High Contracting Parties to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects* (23 December 2016) [CCW/CONFV/10](#).

7 *Report of the 2018 Session of the Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems* (23 October 2018) [CCW/GGE.1/2018/3](#) para 21; *Report of the 2019 Session of the Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems* (25 September 2019) [CCW/GGE.1/2019/3](#) annex IV; *Final Report of the 2019 Meeting of the High Contracting Parties to the Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects* (13 December 2019) [CCW/MSP/2019/9](#) annex III, para (e).

In 2019, Argentina circulated a questionnaire regarding legal reviews, although no information has been made public as to the responses received.⁸ In 2020, States submitted national commentaries on the guiding principles, and in that context some States put on the record their views on the above-quoted principle concerning legal reviews.⁹ During the 2023 GGE meeting, legal reviews were a dedicated discussion topic, leading more than 20 States to express their views on the role and significance of legal reviews. At the end of the 2023 session, the GGE adopted a report, the conclusions of which, among other things, state as follows: 'In this context, the voluntary exchange of relevant best practices between States is encouraged, bearing in mind national security considerations or commercial restrictions on proprietary information.'¹⁰

In conclusion, the GGE has recognised the need for, and significantly raised awareness about, legal reviews, which may be an unanticipated outcome of the GGE that goes beyond the specific context of AWS. At the same time, many participants do not appreciate the key role legal reviews play in the national implementation of any instrument that the GGE may adopt. Also, most GGE participants have so far been relatively reluctant to speak about the specific challenges created by autonomy for the legal review process.

2.2 United Nations General Assembly

The protracted nature of the GGE discussions and the uncertainty about the prospect of reaching a final consensus agreement has led some States to look for alternative fora to progress the debate. In particular, Austria has led the way in terms of raising the issue of AWS in the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) and its Disarmament Committee (First Committee). Thus, in 2021, Austria delivered a joint statement on behalf of 70 States, which recognised that new technologies 'could help to better protect civilians in conflict in certain circumstances' but that AWS also 'raise serious concerns from humanitarian, legal, security, technological and ethical perspectives' and that there is 'urgent need' to adopt 'appropriate rules and measures' to address risks and challenges and a 'necessity for human beings to exert appropriate control, judgement and involvement in relation to the use of weapons systems' to ensure any use complies with international law.¹¹

In 2023, UNGA adopted a resolution on lethal autonomous weapons systems,¹² sponsored by Austria and a number of other States. With 152 votes in favour, 4 against and 11 abstentions,¹³ UNGA expressed its concern about the possible negative consequences and impact of AWS on global security and regional and international stability, and affirmed that international law, in particular the UN Charter, IHL, and international human rights law, applied to AWS. UNGA highlighted the need for the international community to address the challenges and concerns raised by AWS, in particular through the GGE. UNGA further requested the UN Secretary-General to seek the views of States and invite the views of other stakeholders on addressing the legal, ethical, humanitarian and security risks associated with AWS, and to submit a substantive report on the way forward.

The Secretary-General invited submissions in line with this resolution and released a report with a consolidated summary of elements from the submissions received from Member States and Observer States. The report includes definitions and characterisations; challenges, concerns and potential benefits; deliberations by States; next

8 Argentina, *Questionnaire on the Legal Review Mechanisms of New Weapons, Means and Methods of Warfare* (29 March 2019) [CCW/GGE.1/2019/WP.6](#).

9 See *Chairperson's Summary* (19 April 2021) [CCW/GGE.1/2020/WP.7](#), Annex III.

10 *Report of the 2023 session of the Group of Governmental Experts on Emerging Technologies in the Area of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems* (23 May 2023) [CCW/GGE.1/2023/2](#) para 23.

11 *Joint Statement on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems* (UNGA First Committee, 77th United Nations General Assembly (21 October 2022) <[reachingcriticalwill.org/images/documents/Disarmament-fora/1com/1com22/statements/21Oct_LAWS.pdf](#)>.

12 UNGA Res 78/241 (22 December 2023).

13 *General Assembly: Plenary Meeting – Item 99 – A/78/409 DR XXXIII as a Whole – Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems* (22 December 2023 4:01:17 PM) <[reachingcriticalwill.org/images/documents/Disarmament-fora/1com/1com23/votes/L56-GA.pdf](#)>.

steps; and the observations and conclusions of the Secretary-General.¹⁴ The report summarises the issue of legal reviews in two paragraphs:

37. Several States stressed the importance of conducting legal reviews of weapons, means and methods of warfare, as required in article 36 of Protocol I Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 1949. It was noted that the possible unpredictability of lethal autonomous weapons systems raised challenges for the conduct of such legal reviews. It was suggested that legal reviews include aspects of human-machine interaction and how they were addressed in training. The view was expressed that legal reviews were insufficient on their own to address the concerns raised by lethal autonomous weapons systems, and that specific rules were required. Reference was made to two expert meetings on the legal reviews of autonomous weapons systems that were held in Australia in 2023 and 2024.

38. It was noted that there was no provision governing how legal reviews should be conducted and no requirement to publicize the outcome of such reviews. Several States emphasized the utility of voluntary exchanges of information and practices regarding the legal review of lethal autonomous weapons systems.

¹⁴ *Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems: Report of the Secretary-General* (1 July 2024) [A/79/88](#).

3 Developments in legal review practice

3.1 Australia

Australia ratified AP I in June 1991.¹⁵ Up until 2005, legal reviews for the Australian Defence Force (ADF) were conducted on an ad hoc basis. In June 2005, the process was formalised in a Defence Instruction by setting out the initial framework for roles and responsibilities within the ADF.¹⁶ The overall responsibility for conducting reviews was vested with the Director-General Australian Defence Force Legal Service (now Director-General Military Legal Service) and extended to weapons developed, acquired or modified after 1 June 2005 and which were not already operational with the ADF. In practice, the reviews were performed by the Directorate for Operations and International Law (DOIL) upon request by an authorised agency (at the time: Defence Capability Development Group or Defence Materiel Organisation).

In May 2020, the process was revised to seamlessly integrate legal reviews into the Defence acquisition process, with article 36 advice guiding the decision-making at a senior Defence or government level on whether to procure a new defence capability.

Between 2022 and 2023 the process underwent further adjustments, following the Brereton Report (Afghanistan Inquiry Report)¹⁷ which found that the ADF possessed weapons and munitions which had not been subject to a legal review and recommended an audit of all such Defence capabilities, including capabilities which had been in service prior to Australia ratifying AP I. As a result, Australia is currently conducting 'historical' reviews of those capabilities to satisfy the recommendations of the Brereton Report. Notably, Australia also took steps to allow the legal review process to meet the demands of 2023 Defence Strategic Review,¹⁸ including adjusting to tighter time frames and enabling faster review outcomes where capabilities are acquired expeditiously, shifting traditional procurement timelines of years to a matter of months.

Australia's Guide to the Legal Review of New Weapons, Means or Methods of Warfare ('ADF Guide')¹⁹ builds upon the 2005 Defence Instruction but also takes a significant

15 See Australia: *Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I)*, 8 June 1977, International Committee of the Red Cross <ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/api-1977/state-parties>.

16 Australian Department of Defence, *Defence Instruction (General) OPS 44-1: Legal Review of New Weapons* (2 June 2005) (no longer in force).

17 Inspector-General of The Australian Defence Force, *Afghanistan Inquiry Report* (2020) <www.defence.gov.au/sites/default/files/2021-10/IGADF-Afghanistan-Inquiry-Public-Release-Version.pdf>.

18 Australian Government, Defence, *National Defence: Defence Strategic Review 2023* (2023) <www.defence.gov.au/about/reviews-inquiries/defence-strategic-review>.

19 See Department of Defence, *Australia's Guide to the Legal Review of New Weapons, Means or Methods of Warfare* (March 2023, as amended 10 April 2024) <files.apils.org/au/240410_adf_guide_to_art_36_legal_review.pdf>; see also *Enhancing the Legal Review* (n 1) section 2.1.

step forward by providing capability managers who request a legal review with a deeper understanding of the considerations that inform the review process.

The ADF Guide has three parts: Part 1 outlines definitions, the process, and responsibilities for conducting legal reviews; Part 2 elaborates on the scope of article 36 of AP I as traditionally interpreted and applied by Australia; and Part 3 encompasses additional considerations necessary for the review of AWS.²⁰

In March 2023, to complement the ADF Guide, DOIL introduced a certification course for military legal officers willing to conduct legal reviews. The course encompasses a carefully crafted curriculum designed to equip participants with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively carry out legal reviews and includes an assessment to ensure that participants demonstrate required competency. The course allowed to substantially expand the pool of legal officers qualified to perform legal reviews for the ADF. In particular, the second iteration of the course in November 2023 focused on the reserve forces and resulted in a cohort of 60 military reserve lawyers successfully completing the certification program which has built a solid base of expertise for the performance of the ‘historic’ legal reviews mentioned previously.

Another important complementary initiative was the introduction of a new form (in a PDF format) which streamlines the assessment process and facilitates its proper recording.²¹ The form allows the requestor (usually a capability manager) to fill in the necessary details and attach supplementary documentation to enable DOIL to conduct the required assessment. The review is performed and signed off by two officers (with the second reviewer being a senior officer with a relevant delegation to approve the review) and is then counter-signed by the requestor.

Australia considers its article 36 legal review process ‘a work in progress’ and anticipates that both the ADF Guide and the format of the review will continue evolving. In particular, Part 3 of the Guide which focuses on the review of autonomous functionalities of military capabilities will likely see revisions in the future.²²

Australia views its article 36 legal review process as ‘A practice’, not ‘THE practice’, is willing to share information on its process and welcomes feedback upon it.

3.2 New Zealand²³

New Zealand ratified AP I in February 1988.²⁴ The process for a legal review of military capabilities in New Zealand must be viewed in the context in which New Zealand’s armed forces operate and in light of its military doctrine which, as a matter of policy, closely mirrors that of Australia, with allowances for certain national distinction. New Zealand perceives its armed forces operating in an allied environment and therefore places significant emphasis on interoperability of the systems it operates.

Almost invariably, major weapon systems that New Zealand procures and employs are in arsenals of its ‘Five Eyes’ partners, which offers the advantage that these military capabilities would have typically undergone a legal review by a selling allied State. Generally, New Zealand’s legal review process shares many commonalities with the processes established in Australia and the United States. Reviews are conducted centrally at a strategic level within the Operations and International Law Directorate. No distinction is made between AWS and other weapon systems: all weapon systems are reviewed in the same manner. The focus of New Zealand’s review process is on conducting its assessment on a case by case basis, thereby expanding its knowledge through each individual evaluation.

Where New Zealand stands out from its allies and other States, is the inclusion of non-legal considerations – such as ‘the public conscience’ reflective of ‘a “New Zea-

20 See also *Enhancing the Legal Review* (n 1) section 2.1.

21 See Department of Defence, AF172: Article 36 Legal Review Report (16 November 2023) <files.apils.org/au/af172_legal_review_report.pdf>.

22 See also *Enhancing the Legal Review* (n 1) section 2.1.

23 For further detail on the legal review process in New Zealand, see *Enhancing the Legal Review* (n 1) section 2.3.

24 See New Zealand: *Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I)*, 8 June 1977, International Committee of the Red Cross <ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/api-1977/state-parties>.

land way” of action and behaviour with a focus on kindness and tolerance’ – in a legal review process. For example, the Māori notion of kaitiakitanga which stands for guardianship and protection of the natural environment finds its way into the legal review practice when an assessment is made on whether a weapon or munition causes widespread, long-term or severe damage to the natural environment.²⁵

3.3 Singapore²⁶

While Singapore is not a party to AP I, it reviews weapon systems as part of a rigorous defence procurement process. These reviews are conducted at each stage of capability development, planning, delivery and sustainment in a systematic and coordinated manner involving relevant stakeholders and decision makers.

Singapore takes the safety and reliability of its weapons systems seriously, and is continually looking to draw from the best practices of other States. To that end and having acceded to the CCW, Singapore has been actively participating in international discussions, such as the GGE. In addition, Singapore co-hosted regional consultations in the frame of the Responsible AI in the Military Domain Summit (‘REAIM’) process and is co-hosting the 2024 REAIM Summit with the Republic of Korea and the Kingdom of the Netherlands. The above underscores Singapore’s longstanding commitment to uphold international law and promote the responsible use of emerging technologies in accordance with IHL.

3.4 Sweden²⁷

The legal review process in Sweden is governed by the Ordinance on International Law Review of Weapons Projects.²⁸ The Ordinance mandates the Delegation for International Law Review of Weapons (‘Delegation’) to conduct legal reviews of ‘weapons projects’ and relevant agencies – the Swedish Armed Forces, Swedish Defence Materiel Administration, the Swedish Defence Research Agency and others (such as Swedish Police Force and Swedish Customs) – to report on the planned weapons projects to the Delegation as early as feasible. Other agencies and corporations may also submit their weapons projects to the Delegation.

The Delegation reviews ‘weapons and methods of warfare’. Weapons are likely interpreted broadly to also include ‘means of warfare’ in the sense of article 36 of AP I. In the conduct of legal reviews, the Delegation takes into account international human rights law (IHRL) applicable in armed conflict and customary international law.

The Delegation is led by the head of the Legal Department of the Swedish Ministry of Defence with the number of members in the Delegation ranging between eight and ten. As a matter of policy, the Delegation follows a multi-disciplinary approach: it includes experts from a variety of backgrounds, including legal, operational, medical, technical, and others. The Delegation makes its decisions on the basis of unanimity.

While the Delegation has to follow-up on ‘significant weapons projects’ after completing a review, it remains unclear what constitutes such a project; no public information is available as to whether this has happened in practice. In 2023, the Delegation reviewed some systems with autonomous functions, including certain loitering munitions.

25 Tim Wood, ‘AWS Legal Review Series – Inclusion of Quasi-legal Considerations’ (*Articles of War*, 12 March 2024) <lieber.westpoint.edu/inclusion-quasi-legal-considerations/> .

26 This text was supplied by Singapore and lightly edited by the authors of this Report.

27 For further detail on the legal review process in Sweden, see *Enhancing the Legal Review* (n 1) section 2.4.

28 Förordning om folkrättslig granskning av vapenprojekt [Ordinance on International Law Review of Weapons Projects] (15 November 2007), Swedish Code of Statutes, SFS 2007:936.

3.5 Switzerland

The legal review process in Switzerland is largely guided by two documents: MOD Ordinance (DDPS) OMat²⁹ and the Chief of Defence (CHOD) Directive on Cooperation between Defence and Armasuisse (procurement agency); the latter document is currently not publicly available.

Article 11 of OMat mandates legal reviews of weapon systems which are newly acquired, modified or put to a novel or different use, on compliance with applicable international law (para. 1), provides the definition of ‘weapons systems’ which must be subject to a legal review (para. 2), and directs that the procurement agency duly consults the authority designated to independently carry out legal reviews (i.e. the IHL office within the Swiss Armed Forces) and supplies the designated authority with relevant information (para. 3). The provision is reflective of the key gateways in the procurement process – that is initialisation, conceptualisation, realisation and introduction of the weapon system – and mandates that an assessment of compliance with international law be made prior to the development of the concept of the weapon system and its introduction in the Swiss Armed Forces (para. 4).

The legal review process is reasonably flexible but follows a standardised template. In particular, the reviewing authority is required to consider whether a weapon system under review:

- causes superfluous injury or unnecessary suffering;
- is inherently indiscriminate;
- causes particularly serious environmental harm, or
- contravenes any specific prohibitions or restrictions on weapons under international law.

The reviewing authority also considers IHRL and possible future developments in law and policy where necessary.

The reviewing authority focuses its assessment on the designed and intended use of the particular weapon system. Other methods of warfare (such as tactics, techniques and procedures (‘TTPs’)) are reviewed for compliance with international law through ordinary consultations within the Ministry of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport, and not as part of the OMat review process.

The review results in one of the following outcomes:

- non-approval;
- approval with conditions; or
- unconditional approval of the weapon system.

A non-approval is binding for the procurement agency and terminates the procurement process. An approval with conditions translates into binding constraints for the procurement agency and for the (future) user of the weapon, which in the latter case will be integrated in the user manual.

In its arms control and disarmament strategy 2022–2025, the Swiss Federal Council extensively addresses the topic of autonomous weapons systems and artificial intelligence.³⁰ The Swiss approach focuses on compliance with international law and ensuring human control. Switzerland considers the legal review (of AWS) to be one of several elements to ensure a sufficient degree of human control.

The existing Swiss review process is flexible and can be adapted as required for the review of AWS in order to take into account the special characteristics of weapon systems with increasing autonomy. For example, the human-machine interaction can be examined in detail or special training needs of the operators can be addressed.

²⁹ Federal Department of Defence, Civil Protection and Sport, *Ordonnance du DDPS sur l’acquisition, l’utilisation et la mise hors service du matériel* = *Verordnung des VBS über die Beschaffung, die Nutzung und die Ausserdienststellung von Material [Directive on the Material of the Armed Forces]* RS 514.20 / AS 2018 1391 (26 March 2018).

³⁰ Swiss Confederation, Arms Control and Disarmament Strategy (Swiss Federal Department of Foreign Affairs, 2022) <www.eda.admin.ch/dam/eda/en/documents/aussenpolitik/strategien/strategie-ruestungskontrolle-und-abruestung-2022-2025-EN.pdf>.

Switzerland is willing to share information on its process and supports the exchange of best practices between States in the field of the legal review of weapons.

3.6 United Kingdom³¹

The UK ratified AP I in January 1998.³² While legal reviews of military capabilities had been performed prior to that date on an ad hoc basis, ratification of AP I prompted the establishment of a structured process for these reviews. The process is facilitated by serving military lawyers and has significantly developed since its introduction.³³ Importantly, although article 36 legal reviews constitute a significant component of the UK MOD's international law compliance processes, they are just one element within the broader defense framework aimed at ensuring the lawful deployment of military capabilities.

The spectrum of capabilities subject to the legal review is broad, with their selection guided by definitional parameters aligned to those proposed by William Boothby.³⁴ Accordingly, 'weapons and means of warfare' in the sense of an article 36 review cover a range of systems designed or used to injure or kill personnel or damage or destroy property. These capabilities need not be physical and include cyber capabilities. Where weapons or means are 'significantly modified', they become subject to a further legal review. 'Methods of warfare' are equally defined broadly and extend beyond 'normal' or 'anticipated' uses of weapons to ways in which warfare is conducted.

The standard of the legal review requires that the capability is assessed for its compliance with specific prohibitions or restrictions under treaty law and CIL; the reviewing authority equally takes into consideration future developments in law and policy.

The legal review is similar to the Swiss process, in that it is conducted at certain 'gateway' points in the weapons procurement cycle. As a rule, it is an iterative process with the final legal advice delivered prior to the introduction of capability into the UK military's force structures. Early engagement with the reviewing authority – that is at the 'initial' service gate – is encouraged, so that the latter could meaningfully direct the development of capability and the manner in which evidence about its performance is compiled. As a rule, a review is conducted by one lawyer. One lawyer per service is posted on a rotational basis to support the conduct of reviews, to ensure the necessary 'investment' of each of the services in the discharge of the article 36 obligation.

In recent times, the reviewing authority has faced mounting pressure to address 'urgent' requests for legal reviews. These requests often lack information needed to perform the required legal assessment, which places additional strain on a relatively small team comprising six lawyers who are responsible for resolving issues of operations and international law, including space, cyber operations, current operations, and others. Other challenges that the team is facing include the need to manage risks effectively, particularly in accurately interpreting technical terminology and matching this interpretation to relevant legal criteria. The erosion of corporate ('institutional') memory of the legal review process coupled with occasional lapses in recognising its significance within the organisation also continue to pose concerns. The team has therefore taken upon itself the task of educating the services about the nature and scope of the legal review requirement. Recently, decisions were made for both the UK Space Command and the National Cyber Force to assign their own personnel to conduct legal reviews. However, as of the date of writing, there have been no reports of any reviews being carried out by either element.

31 For further detail on the legal review process in the United Kingdom, see *Enhancing the Legal Review* (n 1) section 2.5.

32 See United Kingdom: *Protocol Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts (Protocol I)*, 8 June 1977, International Committee of the Red Cross <ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/api-1977/state-parties>.

33 See generally Development, Concepts and Doctrine Centre, UK Ministry of Defence, *UK Weapon Reviews* (11 March 2016).

34 William H Boothby, *Weapons and the Law of Armed Conflict* (Cambridge University Press, 2nd edn, 2016).

In September 2021, the UK announced its National AI Strategy.³⁵ Building upon it, the Defence AI Strategy was released in June 2022.³⁶ One of the key priorities identified by the government in the latter strategy was to develop and embed an ambitious, safe, and responsible approach to AI in Defence (section 6.1). The government's policy statement, that develops this priority further, explicitly addresses the issue of AWS.³⁷ Accordingly, the UK opposes 'the creation and use of systems that would operate without meaningful and context-appropriate human involvement throughout their lifecycle'.³⁸ Legal reviews under article 36 and other compliance processes within the UK military system (including operational legal advice under article 82 of AP I) are all set to ensure the requisite level of human involvement in the use of military capabilities.

A number of organisations within Defence were tasked to deliver within their respective mandates on the Defence AI Strategy objectives (for example, the Defence Artificial Intelligence Centre (DAIC)). One current challenge for authorities conducting legal reviews is to establish and sustain mutually beneficial cooperation with these organisations which would allow for meaningful integration of operational practices and processes.

3.7 United States

In the US, each of the military services is responsible for reviewing weapon systems it develops or acquires.³⁹ The US subscribes to a weapon acquisition process that includes both legal and policy review requirements. This includes the requirement for a legal review for everything meeting the definition of weapon or weapon systems, but also extends to additional legal and policy reviews specific to AWS.

The US views legal reviews of weapons as best practice to implement customary international law and international treaty law relating to weapons and their use in armed conflict. The US began formally reviewing the legality of weapons in the 1970s, prior to AP I's drafting.⁴⁰ Prior to that, the US informally reviewed weapons, with the earliest being the 1918 review of whether the Winchester pump action shotgun firing buckshot pellets caused unnecessary suffering.

The legal review process in the US is closely tied to the acquisition authority: The component within the Department of Defense (DoD) that acquires or develops weapons is responsible for the legal review.⁴¹ For example, the Army, Navy, and Air Force (military services) and Cyber Command and Special Operations Command (Combatant Commands) have weapons acquisition authority, and are required to review the legality of weapons they acquire or develop.

A DoD policy (DoD Directive 5000.01) requires that the acquisition or procurement of DoD weapons be consistent with all applicable domestic and international law, including international humanitarian law (IHL). To implement this requirement, the directive also requires that '[a]n attorney authorized to conduct such legal reviews in the Department shall conduct the legal review of the intended acquisition of weapons or weapons systems'.

Importantly, legal reviews of weapons conducted by individual services are separate to policy reviews of AWS which are performed at the Department of Defence (DoD) level. Where a request for review is submitted and the capability qualifies as 'a weapon/weapon system', the service receiving the request conducts the review and signs off on it. Where capability is identified as an AWS, DoD conducts the review of that

35 HM Government, *National AI Strategy* (September 2021) <assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/614db4d1e90e077a2cbdf3c4/National_AI_Strategy_-_PDF_version.pdf>.

36 Ministry of Defence, *Defence Artificial Intelligence Strategy* (June 2022) <www.gov.uk/government/publications/defence-artificial-intelligence-strategy/defence-artificial-intelligence-strategy>.

37 Ministry of Defence, *Ambitious, Safe, Responsible: Our Approach to the Delivery of AI-enabled Capability in Defence* (June 2022) Annex C <assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/62a9b1d1e90e07039e31b8cb/20220614-Ambitious_Safe_and_Responsible.pdf>.

38 Ibid.

39 See *Enhancing the Legal Review* (n 1) section 2.6.

40 See *ibid.*

41 See *ibid.*

system on its compliance with relevant policy requirements in addition to a legal review of the system conducted by the respective service (DoD Directive 3000.09).

Weapon systems that have certain autonomous functions are subject to additional reviews to ensure that the design allows the exercise of appropriate levels of human judgment in their use. DoD Directive 3000.09 requires two separate reviews by senior officials prior to the formal development and fielding of weapon systems with certain autonomous functions.

The first such review occurs before a weapon system enters formal development. At this stage, senior officials must ensure that:

- ‘The system design incorporates the necessary capabilities to allow commanders and operators to exercise appropriate levels of human judgment over the use of force’;
- ‘The system is designed to complete engagements in a timeframe consistent with commander and operator intentions, and if unable to do so, to terminate engagements or seek additional human operator input before continuing the engagement’;
- ‘The system design ... addresses and minimizes the probability and consequences of failures that could lead to unintended engagements or to loss of control of the system’, which would include a review of safeties, anti-tamper mechanisms, and information systems security;
- ‘Plans are in place for [verification and validation,] and [operational test and evaluation] to establish system reliability, effectiveness, and suitability under realistic conditions, including possible adversary actions, to a sufficient standard consistent with the potential consequences of an unintentional engagement or loss of control of the system’.

In the second phase, before fielding of such a weapon system, senior officials will also ensure:

- The system design requirements have been implemented to standard;
- The verification and validation, and operational test and evaluation adequately assess system performance, capability, reliability, effectiveness, and suitability under realistic conditions;
- ‘System capabilities, human-machine interfaces, doctrine, [tactics, techniques, and procedures, also known as TTPs], and training have demonstrated the capability to allow commanders and operators to exercise appropriate levels of human judgment in the use of force and to employ systems with appropriate care and in accordance with the law of war, applicable treaties, weapon system safety rules, and applicable ROE (or rules of engagement)’;
- ‘Adequate training, TTPs, and doctrine are available, periodically reviewed, and used by system operators and commanders to understand the functioning, capabilities, and limitations of the system’s autonomy in realistic operational conditions’;
- ‘System design and human-machine interfaces are readily understandable to trained operators, provide traceable feedback on system status, and provide clear procedures for trained operators to activate and deactivate system functions’; and finally,
- ‘A [additional] legal review of the weapon system has been completed’.

As a result, weapon systems with certain autonomous functions receive two legal reviews instead of one – one review before formal development and one review prior to fielding.

3.8 International Committee of the Red Cross⁴²

Considering the pivotal role played by the ICRC both in the development of IHL and the promotion of its national implementation (including through legal reviews), it is important to take note of the views of the ICRC in context of ongoing international debates about AWS.

42 This text was supplied by the ICRC and lightly edited by the authors of this Report.

The ICRC understands the term ‘autonomous weapon system’ as a weapon system that is designed to select and engage one or more targets without the need for human intervention after activation. The process by which AWS function entails loss of human control and judgement in the use of force, bringing risks for civilians, challenges for IHL compliance and fundamental ethical concerns for humanity. Due to these risks, the ICRC recommends that States adopt new legally binding rules that explicitly prohibit unpredictable AWS, being those that are designed or used in a manner such that their effects cannot be sufficiently understood, predicted and explained; and antipersonnel AWS, being those designed or used to apply force against human beings. Furthermore, the design and use of AWS that would not be prohibited should be regulated, including through a combination of:

- restricting targets to only those which are military objectives by nature;
- limiting the location, time and situation in which the AWS is operating, including to avoid concentrations of civilians or civilian objects;
- limiting the number of engagements that the AWS can undertake;
- ensuring, to the maximum extent feasible, the ability for a human user to:
 - effectively supervise, and
 - in a timely manner intervene and, where appropriate, deactivate operation of the AWS;
- AWS that do not allow a human user to do so, must be equipped with an effective self-destruction, self-deactivation or self-neutralization mechanism, designed so that the AWS will no longer function as an AWS when it no longer serves the military purpose for which it was launched.⁴³

The ICRC notes the critical importance of legal reviews in ensuring that a State’s armed forces comply with IHL, in light of the rapid development and use of new and emerging technologies of warfare, but also recognizes the challenges involved. While robust legal reviews are essential, they are not a sufficient response on their own to the concerns raised by AWS and cannot substitute the need for States to agree on new international law rules on AWS. That said, legal reviews will remain a critical tool to operationalise and ensure compliance with specific prohibitions and restrictions on AWS, once set in a legally binding instrument that clarifies and develops existing rules.

The reviewing authority needs to review any new weapons, means and methods of warfare that a State develops or acquires, which encompass not only weapons to be newly acquired by a State, but also existing weapons that are modified, either in their physical properties or through software updates or modifications, in a way that alters their function or impacts their effects. Changes to the weapons in terms of their physical or digital properties should also be reviewed. With respect to AWS, in particular if incorporating AI or machine learning, a legal review conducted before its use (or deployment) risks being invalidated following activation as the software modifies itself, leading to a change in the parameters on which the system was reviewed.

In addition to IHL and international disarmament law, the reviewing authority needs to consider other rules of international law applicable to the State, such as international human rights law, law of the sea, space law, and international environmental law. Consideration should be given to whether the weapon complies with the Martens clause. A weapon or means of warfare cannot be assessed in isolation from the ways in which it is used. The intrinsic link between weapons, means and methods of warfare poses the question of the relevance of IHL rules on the conduct of hostilities to legal reviews. A reviewer would need to consider all reasonably foreseeable strikes that the AWS could carry out in its normal or expected circumstances and method of use, and ultimately be satisfied that the autonomy in the weapon’s critical functions (i.e. target selection and engagement) still allows the human user to comply with their obligations under the IHL rules on the conduct of hostilities.

43 ICRC, Submission on Autonomous Weapon Systems to the United Nations Secretary-General (March 2024) <www.icrc.org/en/document/autonomous-weapons-icrc-submits-recommendations-un-secretary-general>.

The logical outcome of a review process of an AWS would be the following: AWS that are designed or used in a manner such that their effects cannot be sufficiently understood, predicted and explained must not be approved by the reviewing authorities, notably because of their indiscriminate effects. For AWS that are not prohibited per se, the reviewing authority must ensure that conditions for or restrictions on the method and circumstances of use specific to the weapon system under review are clearly articulated. Appropriate regulations must be enforced through practical control measures. Human control must be preserved over the use of force and the effects of AWS, and should be a central consideration to satisfy the legality of an AWS in its normal or expected circumstances and method of use.

The existing approach to legal reviews required adaptation. This includes sources of data used to test AWS, in particular systems incorporating AI and learning capabilities, and legal risk identified from test and evaluation stages. The assessment of the legality of the new weapon, means or method of warfare is based on the weapon's technical characteristics, functioning and design-dependent effects, taking into account a range of military, technical, health and environmental factors. In light of this complexity, experts from various disciplines need to be involved in the review process. Among others, when examining the weapon's mechanism of injury, the reviewing authority should take into account the potential gendered and other differentiated impacts to the furthest extent possible, including by using sex-, disability- and age-disaggregated data, of the weapon's effects on humans.

Article 36 is complemented by Article 82 of AP I. Both provisions establish a framework to ensure armed forces are conducting operations within the limits of IHL. But there are questions as to how the interaction between these two provisions looks in practice, in light of the increased frequency of change to the functioning of certain weapons after the initial legal review has been conducted.

States need to interpret and apply IHL into the review process for AWS and contribute to State practice which is critical due to the complexity and sophisticated nature of the AWS. Increased transparency is required with respect to the legal review mechanisms, and would be desirable to the review outcomes.

4 Thematic overview of workshop discussions

This part briefly outlines some of the discussions that emerged during the meeting. They are not necessarily tied to a particular element or session of the workshop but reflect overarching issues that were raised by meeting participants and discussed across the meeting.

4.1 Locating legal reviews

Numerous participants explained that legal reviews are but one component of ensuring that new weapons, means or methods are compliant with a State's legal obligations, as well as sitting within its wider policy framework. Many participants noted that legal reviews are not a standalone tool to achieve international law assurance, but are embedded within, or sit alongside, other processes that complement and/or influence the legal review, such as acquisition processes, and other regulatory frameworks, including domestic law or policies.

While this is not a novelty introduced by AWS, some of the related technologies – such as AI – have triggered the creation of new policy frameworks.

Participants pointed out that synchronising those policy requirements with a legal review may at times be challenging. Some argued that a legal review process may be best placed to assess whether a given AWS complies with the wider policy framework, while others favoured distinct processes for reviewing compatibility with other policy frameworks.

4.2 Lexicon

Many participants agreed that States will likely need to define key terms used in a legal review. After all, legal reviews are not done in isolation but typically rely on inputs from other fields of expertise. Definitions may relate to legal terms, such as the meaning of 'methods of warfare', but also non-legal terms such as 'use case' or 'machine learning'.

Participants found it important to have some uniformity in the use of key terms as legal reviews would typically rely on evidence provided by non-lawyers such as engineers or programmers and by State entities or private companies. Some participants noted that not only would lawyers and experts from other fields frequently have different understandings of the same term, it would also be common even among engineers or programmers to interpret a given term differently, depending on their particular background or expertise. A common understanding of key terms would therefore not only help to enhance the accessibility of the outcome of the legal review but also facilitate the discussion of everyone involved in and contributing to a legal review.

One approach that was proposed was to create a 'lexicon' of key terms and their respective definitions. The identification of what terms are relevant and how they ought to be defined could be a valuable process of identifying otherwise unnoticed misunderstandings and of gaining mutual understanding between the various involved experts.

4.3 Legal reviews of weapons/means and legal reviews of methods

While participants underlined that it would be impossible to review a weapon completely isolated from how it is intended to be used, for non-AWS, the method of use typically receives less attention in a legal review. Consequently, much of the well-established practices and procedures for legal reviews have a focus on the weapon and appear to review methods more as a byproduct. However, as some participants of the meeting pointed out, with the legality of the use of a given AWS more dependant on the circumstances of use (for instance of the type of target it is ought to be used against, or of procedural aspects, such as to who authorises the use of an AWS), a legal review of AWS may need to put more emphasis on the method of use. How a review of methods ought to be done and whether the processes and the involved expertise would require adaptation was not the focus of attention and was not settled during the meeting.

Other participants, while not necessarily disagreeing with this argument, expressed some caution about the statement that methods require more attention in a legal review of AWS. When legal reviews put more emphasis on the method, it is important not to overextend their scope to turn the review into an assessment that is beyond the intended outcome that legal reviews are designed for. Specifically, it was proposed that the legal review cannot be extended to address the issue of the actual use of a weapon, means or method in a specific context. These participants pointed out that a legal review cannot and should not replace the judgment of commanders in operational settings or operational legal advice.

Some participants noted that the existing process for reviewing methods or means was through the standalone legal advice of processes, doctrine, standard operating procedures and TTPs before they were introduced into service, not specifically considered as a legal review in the sense that capabilities were reviewed in a discrete way. In this respect, the review of means and methods of warfare was considered by some participants as being part of standing business processes.

4.4 Legal review as process versus outcome

The participants of the meeting discussed whether a legal review should be primarily seen as a process or as an outcome. Traditionally, and for the review of non-AWS, legal reviews are often seen as a procedure that culminates in a document that either: approves the weapon, means or method of warfare; approves it with certain conditions or considers its use as entirely unlawful. However, with AWS, and as a result of some of the technologies used, some participants advocated that legal reviews should be considered more as an ongoing process that accompanies a weapon during its entire life-cycle. Rather than being a one-off outcome, legal reviews would periodically be conducted for as long as a particular weapon, means or method of warfare was in the inventory of a state. For instance, because AWS may have some learning capabilities and their characteristics may continuously evolve, periodic, if not constant re-reviews may be seen as necessary.

Contrary to this view, however, some participants noted that while legal reviews were an important tool to enable compliance with IL, it remains primarily up to commanders and their operational legal advisors to assess whether the use of a given weapon, means or method of warfare was lawful in a particular context. It was noted by some participants that a continuous review process may have the potential to blur the distinction between legal reviews and operational use of a weapon, means or method of warfare (and associated legal advice with respect to the use of that weapon, means or method).

4.5 Multidisciplinary approach

That legal reviews of new weapons, means or methods may include inputs from State experts in fields of expertise other than law, is well established. This was considered by participants a matter that applies equally to the review of AWS and non-AWS. However, participants discussed whether the technological complexity and the potentially demanding questions of human performance raised by AWS may require a more prominent and permanent role of State experts from other fields than law, such as from technology, psychology or ethics. While there appeared to be consensus that legal reviews should be able to access advice from experts from other fields than law, and have them involved early in the process, participants discussed the role of said non-legal experts. In particular, the role and functional inputs of non-legal experts was discussed, and differing practices implemented by States indicate that the manner in which this non-legal advice should be incorporated into the role could be purely advisory role or as a decision maker with authority to dictate the outcome of the review.

While a multidisciplinary approach in legal reviews was generally acknowledged as a good practice in theory, some participants also pointed out practical problems with involving a wide range of experts, including the absence of certain expertise within civil services, and issues related to security clearances and information sharing.

4.6 Security of autonomous weapon systems

The question of whether and how security ought to be considered in a legal review of new weapons, means or methods of warfare was discussed from a number of different angles.

First, participants raised the question of how security should be understood in the context of a legal review of AWS. Without a clear understanding of the meaning of security it would be difficult to decide if and how security ought to be relevant in a legal review. While it was broadly agreed that States will have to define it for the purpose of their own processes, some discussants argued that security should primarily be understood to refer to the ‘hackability’ of a system. If a system could be easily altered (i.e. hacked) by unauthorised actors and – for instance – the weapon’s target identification system could be easily compromised, then it would be difficult for a State to comply with its legal obligations.

However, some participants questioned whether security considerations should be included in a legal review at all. In their view, targeted interference by an opposing party is the legal responsibility of the respective party, not of the state conducting a legal review. What would need to be considered in a legal review, however, was non-targeted interference that may affect legally relevant functions of the AWS. For instance, if the target identification system of an AWS was affected by mobile phones used by nearby civilians, then such interference would need to be considered in a legal review.

Second, participants discussed when the security of an AWS should be reviewed. It was pointed out that security threats continuously evolve, that new software vulnerabilities may be discovered and that, therefore, the review of sufficient security must be an ongoing process. If the security of legal reviews ought to be a component of a legal review, it should be incorporated into a continuous review process.

4.7 Role of industry

Participants discussed the role of industry in the legal review of AWS. It was pointed out that some private companies conduct their own legal reviews during the development of new weapons, means or methods of warfare in an attempt to determine whether legal issues could arise. While legal reviews conducted by industry do not replace a legal review completed by States, this practice was generally welcomed as a positive development that could ensure that legal considerations are included comprehensively from as early as possible in the development of novel weapon systems.

Furthermore, it was considered as important that industry understands what a legal review involves and how States are approaching the review of the weapons developed and produced by industry. This enables the industry to synchronise their processes with timing and the needs of legal reviews.

Participants considered the role of industry in the testing, evaluation, verification and validation (TEVV) as particularly crucial for the legal reviews of AWS. Having designed and developed a particular weapon or weapon system, industry may have extensive amounts of performance data available that could be used in a legal review. It was, however, also pointed out that where the sharing of data from industry to legal reviewers was considered necessary, it should be made part of the contractual requirements that the designer or developer is obligated to deliver to the purchasing State party (client). Furthermore, where legal reviews have specific data requirements that industry ought to generate, this should be discussed early in the process of design and development.

Participants further discussed to what extent States could trust data provided by capability designers and developers. While it was undisputed that the obligation to legally review new weapons, means or methods of warfare remains that of the State, and that therefore States cannot simply subsume the results of a review conducted by industry, using the data generated by industry was generally considered as possible. Whether a State can trust the data provided by industry would be considered by most participants to be dependent upon a case-by-case assessment regarding the data, its provenance, the relationship between the State and the relevant company, and a number of other factors.

4.8 Information-sharing and transparency

The question of information-sharing and transparency was discussed from two different angles, which participants thought were important to keep separate: first, as information sharing between States themselves, and, second, as information sharing between States and the general public.

Regarding the sharing of information between States, it was considered that States are free to share whatever information they deem useful and appropriate, particularly from the perspective of information security and in respect of disclosures made with security classification protections in mind. The sharing of processes and data, but potentially even of entire review documents, while within discretion of States, may be particularly useful where the receiving State does not have the resources or the knowledge to conduct the necessary TEVV for the specific capability. However, it was broadly agreed by participants that regardless of the extent of information sharing, the receiving State remains entirely responsible to conduct its own legal review.

Regarding the sharing of information with the general public, some participants welcomed this type of information sharing as a useful transparency measure that can enhance public trust in the process and serve as a confidence building measure. However, taking into account the need to balance information security, participants underlined that even States that share information with the general public would typically only publish documents such as the legal basis for the review or a description of their processes, as compared to the outcome of legal reviews, or the data associated with the review. However, one participant pointed to the Netherlands' practice insofar as they publish entire outcome documents, although in a redacted form.

In relation to both types of information sharing, meeting participants generally considered this was central to the enhancing utility of legal reviews as a confidence building measure and contributes to the universalisation of the review process.

5 Conclusion

The number of participants the Expert Meeting attracted and the lively discussions that transpired during the Meeting testify to the significance of legal reviews of weapons, means and methods of warfare as an IHL compliance mechanism. The discussions highlighted how existing legal review mechanisms are both appropriate and necessary when it comes to evaluating the compatibility of AWS with international law. At the same time, there undoubtedly remain some uncertainties and challenges that would benefit from further discussion. Thus, the authors of this report conclude that follow-up meetings with an extended participation would be beneficial, although further consideration should be given to either broadening the discussion to legal reviews generally (that is, not only with respect to AWS) or specifically including challenges posed by other emerging technologies (such as cyber or space capabilities).

During the Expert Meeting, the organising team presented a prototype of an online portal that could serve as a platform to facilitate a voluntary exchange of best practice on the legal review of weapons, means and methods of warfare between States, and to encourage the adoption and development of national legal review practice. The prototype was favourably received by the participants, although some governmental experts raised questions about who would host such a platform.

At the Vienna Conference on Autonomous Weapons System, hosted by the Austrian Federal Ministry for European and International Affairs on 29 and 30 April 2024 – less than two weeks after the Expert Meeting – Ms Izumi Nakamitsu, Under-Secretary-General and High Representative for Disarmament Affairs, announced plans for UNODA to develop an online portal, which would allow States to share policy, practice and lessons learned related to legal reviews with a focus on new and emerging technologies. Subsequent discussions between UNODA and the editors of the prototype portal led to an arrangement whereby UNODA and the newly-established Asia-Pacific Institute for Law and Security (APILS) would work together to develop the portal. The content of the portal would largely follow that of the prototype, namely it would comprise four parts:

1. An overview of the development of legal reviews as a mechanism for assessing compliance with international legal obligations;
2. A collation of statements made by States and other entities in relation to legal reviews in various international and domestic fora;
3. Overviews of the relevant policies and practises of States that undertake legal reviews;
4. A collection of useful resources for States developing the legal review process, or that are interested in doing so, and for officials conducting the reviews.⁴⁴

⁴⁴ For updates, see <apils.org/legal-review>.

The participants of the Expert Meeting were also generally supportive of the proposed Elements of Good Practice, although some governmental experts noted that some of the elements may be redundant or overly prescriptive. Many experts also supported the idea of splitting the elements into two parts, such that one part would pertain to legal review in general and the other part would address issues specific to the review of AWS. Further work on the Elements will also be undertaken by APILS, which will engage in further consultations with governmental and non-governmental experts in due course.⁴⁵

⁴⁵ For updates, see <apils.org/good-practices/>.

Annexes

A Elements of good practice

Introduction

This annex contains a set of good practices that the authors suggest may assist States in carrying out legal reviews of autonomous weapon systems ('AWS') in a manner that accounts for the unique characteristics of these weapon systems. Adoption of these practices can, in the view of the authors, enhance the efficacy of legal reviews as a mechanism for implementing international legal obligations relevant to AWS. Considering that legal reviews are undertaken at the national level and that States have significant discretion in terms of the conduct of the reviews, some or all of these practices could be independently adopted by States, or agreed as representing good practice with other States.

These good practices do not aim to offer an interpretation of existing legal obligations. Indeed, the obligations of States differ when it comes to legal reviews: in particular, not all States are party to Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions ('AP I'), article 36 of which creates a binding obligation to conduct a legal review of weapon systems, including AWS. The practices included in this document could be relevant to all States reviewing AWS, irrespective of whether they have an obligation under international law to do so, and what the scope of that obligation might be. That said, some States may view some of the elements of good practices as flowing from their international legal obligations.

The articulation of these good practices is without prejudice to efforts aimed at clarifying or further developing the current normative framework with respect to the development and use of AWS. These good practices seek to support States in operationalising the Guiding Principles developed and affirmed by the Group of Governmental Experts on Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems ('GGE')⁴⁶ and endorsed by the Meeting of the High Contracting Parties to the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons.⁴⁷ These good practices relate specifically to Guiding Principle (e), which stipulates that '[i]n accordance with States' obligations under international law, in the study, development, acquisition, or adoption of a new weapon, means or method of warfare, determination must be made whether its employment would, in some or all circumstances, be prohibited by international law'.⁴⁸ These good practices are also in line with the most recent report of the GGE, which reaffirmed the Guiding Principle in its conclusions and encouraged the voluntary exchange of relevant best practices between States.⁴⁹

46 2018 GGE Report (n 7) para 21; 2019 GGE Report (n 7) annex IV.

47 2019 Report of the CCW MHCP (n 7) para 31 and annex III.

48 2018 GGE Report (n 7) para 21(d); 2019 GGE Report (n 7) annex IV, para (e); 2019 CCW MHCP Report (n 7) annex III, para (e).

49 2023 GGE Report (n 10) para 23.

Genesis and current status

Work on these good practices began with a comprehensive review of submissions by States and other participants in the GGE. This exercise resulted in a report (first published in March 2023 and reissued with updates in May 2023⁵⁰) that collated these statements. The report extrapolated from these statements an initial list of propositions about legal reviews of AWS.

This list of propositions was presented and discussed during the Expert Meeting on the Legal Review of AWS in Sydney in March 2023 (the 2023 Meeting). Following this meeting, a working group composed of Netta Goussac, Natalia Jevglevskaja, Rain Liivoja and Lauren Sanders – with additional input from Damian Copeland – revised the list into a structured set of Elements of Possible Good Practices in the Legal Review of Autonomous Weapon Systems. These elements were, after a round of written feedback from participants of the 2023 Meeting, refined further and annexed to the report of the meeting.⁵¹

Subsequently, Renato Wolf joined the working group, and drafted commentaries on each of the elements to provide more context and explanation for the benefit of experts who did not participate in the 2023 Meeting. This Annex reproduces the Elements of Possible Good Practices with a few minor textual changes and two further elements (1bis and 7bis) made by the working group. While the commentaries have been omitted from this annex, some of the elements are followed by questions that were raised for discussion in the 2024 Expert Meeting on the Legal Review of AWS.

Terminology

There is no internationally agreed definition of the term ‘autonomous weapon system’. In these good practices, the term refers broadly to any weapon system that, once activated, can select and engage targets without further intervention by an operator. Thus, for the purposes of these good practices, AWS include systems with varying degrees of autonomy. These practices are not intended to be limited to ‘lethal autonomous weapon systems’ (‘LAWS’), a concept used by the GGE.

All AWS, whether capable of lethal effects or not, can create challenges for legal review. In addition, the lack of a lethal effect does not absolve States of their obligations to use capabilities consistently with international law, or of any legal obligation to conduct a pre-emptive review. Possibly because of these reasons, the question of lethality did not arise during the 2023 Expert Meeting, and that factor is therefore not separately addressed in these good practices.

The reference to ‘weapon systems’ indicates that the focus is broader than just the weapon itself (such as a munition). The ‘system’ includes other hardware (eg, sensors and platforms) and software necessary for the operation of the weapon. Importantly, autonomous targeting capability may be enabled at a system-of-systems level rather than through the interaction of subsystems of single weapon systems or platforms. There was no agreement at the 2023 Expert Meeting as to what equipment might be captured by the term ‘system’ or the related international law term ‘means of warfare’.

These good practices refer to the pre-emptive assessment of weapons, means and methods of warfare for compliance with international law as ‘legal review’. This term was preferred over the notion of ‘article 36 review’ because it covers review processes undertaken without any obligation under AP I. Also, ‘legal review’ was seen as preferable to ‘weapons review’ as the purpose of the review is to assess legal compliance; where non-legal considerations are included in the review, they play a secondary role.

50 Rosie Cavdarski, Lauren Sanders, and Rain Liivoja, *Weapons Reviews of Autonomous Weapon Systems: Report on Submissions to the GGE on LAWS* (Version 1.0, University of Queensland, 2023) <doi.org/10.14264/6670709>; Rosie Cavdarski, Lauren Sanders, and Rain Liivoja, *Legal Reviews of Autonomous Weapon Systems: Report on Submissions to the GGE on LAWS* (Version 2.0, University of Queensland, 2023) <doi.org/10.14264/1c0275b>.

51 *Enhancing the Legal Review* (n 1).

Scope of the legal review

1. A State could conduct a legal review, including the review of an AWS, as a result of the State's:

- a. **specific obligation under international law to undertake the review;**
- b. **interpretation of its general obligations to implement international humanitarian law ('IHL'); and/or**
- c. **national law or policy.**

***1bis.* A State should codify its process for legal reviews of AWS in an appropriate document. The review process should be assessed periodically in light of legal and technological changes, and updated as required.**

Questions for discussion

1. Should States codify their process for legal review of AWS?
2. When should the review process and its codification be reassessed?

2. The legal review should identify and assess issues of international law compliance specific to AWS.

3. The legal review should assess whether the AWS can be used in compliance with the reviewing State's applicable international legal obligations. In addition to IHL, these legal obligations may arise from, for example, arms control and disarmament law, international human rights law, international environmental law, law of the sea, space law and *jus contra bellum*.

Questions for discussion

1. Should States consider listing which rules of international law other than IHL ought to be, as a minimum, included in a legal review of AWS? Should States more specifically determine which rules of international law other than IHL would be at risk of not being complied with when using AWS and therefore should be particularly considered in a legal review of an AWS?
2. Other international law rules might not be determinative of whether an AWS is capable of being used in compliance with international law but would be relevant, for example, with respect to limitations placed on the use of the weapon. Should such rules be considered in a legal review?
3. How are States addressing in legal reviews of AWS international law rules that are applicable only in some circumstances of use, for example, rules applicable in international armed conflict that the State considers are not applicable in non-international armed conflict?

4. The legal review of an AWS could assess the ability of the AWS to be used in compliance with rules relating to the conduct of hostilities. This may require considering each anticipated method of use of the AWS.

Questions for discussion:

1. How can/should a legal review assess compliance with conduct of hostilities rules? For example, can/should the legal review address the following questions:
2. Does the AWS and, in particular, the human-machine interaction allow the users to comply with conduct of hostilities rules (see also Element 6)? Can the assessments that international law assigns to particular categories of persons be made by them? For instance, article 57(2)(a) of AP I assigns the assessment of what is feasible to minimise collateral damage to 'those who plan or decide upon attack'. Does the concept of human-machine interaction, including the processes, allow 'those who plan or decide upon an attack' to make this assessment?
3. Does the behaviour of the AWS allow appropriate estimates as to the outcomes of the attack, including the level of civilian casualties and damage to civilian property so the relevant persons can base their assessments, for

instance regarding the proportionality of the expected collateral damage, on those predictions?

4. Can the users be sufficiently certain that the assessments they made and the decisions they took with regards to the targets to be attacked are sufficiently likely to be implemented? For instance, when users determine that they want to use the AWS to attack objects of category X, is the AWS sufficiently likely to only strike such objects?
5. How can/should a legal review assess an anticipated method of use of an AWS?

5. States could articulate criteria for determining which capabilities and systems, including those with autonomous functions, amount to weapons, means or methods of warfare and therefore should be the subject of a legal review.

Questions for discussion

1. What are the criteria for determining which capabilities and systems (including those with autonomous functions) amount to weapons, means, methods of warfare?
2. Is the concept of 'co-production of hostilities' useful to frame the extent of capability under review?
3. When in the development/acquisition process can/should this assessment take place?

Conducting a legal review

Relevant considerations

6. A legal review of an AWS could assess the human-machine interaction to determine whether humans will be able to fulfil their obligations under international law in the use of AWS.

Questions for discussion

1. Does IHL require any particular level and type of human-machine interaction when using AWS?
2. Depending on the answer to this question, how should human-machine interaction be considered in the legal review?
3. Should legal reviews consider when legal obligations may be discharged in the deployment of the AWS?
4. What limitations or caveats could a legal review recommend in relation to human-machine interaction (see Elements 10 and 11)?

7. A legal review of an AWS could assess if, where and how its use would transfer responsibility for acts necessary for complying with international law from one human to another human, and whether such a transfer would be consistent with international law.

7bis. A legal review of an AWS should assess whether physical and cybersecurity controls of the system are adequate to ensure the integrity of the system.

Question for discussion

1. Should the cybersecurity of weapon systems be considered in a legal review?

8. A legal review of an AWS could include a reflection upon additional considerations that the State deems relevant to its use, such as:

- a. **policy constraints;**
- b. **domestic law;**
- c. **security and proliferation risk;**
- d. **ethical and societal implications;**
- e. **possible future development of the law.**

Question for discussion

1. Where a State's legal review of an AWS includes reflection on additional considerations, how does this affect the selection of personnel responsible for, or involved in, the conduct of the legal review?
- 9. Where a legal review addresses issues not based on an international law obligation, the review could make that explicit.**
- 10. A legal review could conclude that the capability's normal or anticipated use is:**
- a. lawful; or
 - b. lawful under certain circumstances or subject to certain conditions; or
 - c. unlawful.
- 11. With respect to the study, development, acquisition and use of AWS, the conditions imposed as a result of the legal review could relate to, for example:**
- a. the characteristics of a system under development;
 - b. the operating environment;
 - c. the approved use case(s) (such as use in a certain type of armed conflict, a particular domain of warfare, or against particular types of targets);
 - d. the approved methods of use;
 - e. degree and type of human-machine interaction;
 - f. the system(s) within which the capability may be integrated.

Questions for discussion

1. What is the meaning of 'use case'? Is this a useful term or interpreted differently from the anticipated use of the AWS?
2. How does a 'method of warfare' differ from a 'use case'?
3. Do we need to consider use cases in a legal review?
4. Should this list be referred to as a non-exhaustive and overlapping list; or should some of the additional descriptors be refined? For example, is domain of warfare part of the operating environment, the approved use case, or both?
5. How should a State give effect to conditions imposed at the legal review stage at the operational stage (Element 17)?

Modifications

- 12. States could articulate what kind of changes would cause the legal review to become inadequate, so as to require a reconsideration of the existing legal review, including:**
- a. changes to the applicable law;
 - b. modifications to a capability or its normal or expected use, following its introduction to service.

Questions for discussion

1. Should this include reference to (or a distinction between) training and testing data?
 2. Could the legal review of certain (minor modifications) be conducted by an operational legal adviser where necessary?
- 13. With respect to AWS, such modifications could include changes to:**
- a. the nature and extent of human-machine interaction;
 - b. system algorithms and datasets;
 - c. intended mission sets;
 - d. intended operational environments;
 - e. intended target sets;
 - f. expected adversarial countermeasures.

Questions for discussion

1. Do the concepts used in this element have distinct meanings?
2. Do these terms mean different things from the 'use case' or 'method of use' of the AWS?
3. Are States legally required to anticipate adversarial countermeasures and consider them in a legal review?

14. States could identify parameters, limits, appropriate safeguards or risk-mitigation measures with respect to the use of technological processes (such as artificial intelligence techniques) that result in modifications.

Questions for discussion

1. Should machine learning capabilities and how to review them be considered separately from other modifications?
2. Should parameters and limits also be included in consideration of this element?

Legal review process

Timing

15. States could commence legal reviews of AWS as early as feasible in the study, development and acquisition processes. States could reconsider legal reviews as often as necessary.

Questions for discussion

1. How can/should legal reviews be integrated into AWS design, development and acquisition processes?
2. What is the earliest point for State involvement in an acquisition process, from a legal review perspective, in relation to the research and development of a capability where the potential future application of that capability is not yet clear?
3. How much involvement is required to conduct legal reviews at the earliest stages of design and development?
4. Should legal review policy extend to when reviews should occur when private companies are studying or developing weapons, means or methods of warfare?

Relationship to other national practices

16. States could articulate how legal reviews are integrated into their broader weapons design and development processes.

Questions for discussion

1. How can the outcomes of legal reviews best be communicated to others who need to know about them? How can a State ensure that relevant information is readily accessible?
2. What is the relationship, if any, between legal reviews of AWS and legal assessments conducted as part of a risk assessment related to a proposed international transfer of an AWS?

17. States could communicate the outcomes of legal reviews to those involved in the review process, as well as operational legal advisers and commanders. This could be facilitated by establishing an appropriately controlled national repository to ensure previous legal reviews can easily be found and accessed.

Questions for discussion

1. What considerations should States bear in mind when communicating about legal reviews, for example, in relation to freedom of information and legal professional privilege?
2. How can the outcomes of legal reviews best be communicated to others who need to know about them?
3. How can a State ensure that relevant information is readily accessible and controlled?

18. States could articulate how legal reviews interact with other policy, administrative and technical frameworks, including control and risk-mitigation measures, in the broader weapons acquisition and use processes.

Questions for discussion

1. How can/should legal reviews interact with a state's other policy, and administrative and technical frameworks?

Participants

19. States could determine the required qualifications of legal reviewers.

Questions for discussion

1. What should be the minimum qualifications of a legal reviewer of an AWS?
2. Should these minimum qualifications be articulated in a State's legal review policy?

20. States could articulate how and by whom legal reviews, including reviews of an AWS or modifications of an AWS, are authorised.

21. States could specify the national authorities for approving modifications of AWS and the legal advice required.

22. States could articulate ways to ensure that the legal review takes a multidisciplinary approach capable of properly assessing functions of the AWS that may affect the user's ability to comply with IHL.

Testing, evaluation, verification and validation

23. States could articulate the requirements for reliable and independent testing, evaluation, verification and validation ('TEVV') of AWS to inform the legal review. States could identify and require the use of:

- a. specific TEVV procedures, methods, environments and protocols;
- b. specific standards or models of performance, including in relation to reliability and predictability.

24. States could independently evaluate:

- a. algorithms and training data sets;
- b. context or use-cases for an AWS.

25. States could articulate what information they require to undertake such evaluations.

Question for discussion

1. Should this Element be combined with Element 24?

26. States could specify the extent to which TEVV of an AWS may be automated.

Question for discussion:

1. Is further information about TEVV required? Such as discussion on how to treat/review testing data (as compared to training data)?

Sharing information about legal reviews

27. An exchange of information pertaining to legal review processes could occur as a result of States’:

- a. obligations under international law to communicate to each other information about laws and regulations giving effect to IHL;
- b. decision to engage, on a voluntary basis, in a broader exchange of information and good practices.

28. An exchange of information pertaining to legal review processes could improve their effectiveness. In relation to AWS, such an exchange could include information about:

- a. if and how the legal review of an AWS differs from a legal review process of a capability that is not an AWS;
- b. what challenges have arisen in conducting legal reviews of AWS;
- c. what novel legal issues have required consideration during the legal review of an AWS.

29. States could establish, and contribute to, a repository for information about processes and practices of legal reviews.

30. Having due regard to national security requirements and the protection of proprietary information, States could also add to the repository select information relating to specific legal reviews of particular AWS. This could include outlining the general type of AWS capabilities, functionality or use contexts that a State considers to be consistent or inconsistent with its obligations under international law.

Question for discussion

1. Should this element separate different kinds of classified information (such as distinguishing between operational and security classifications as compared to commercial-in-confidence information)?

B Scenarios

These scenarios used during the Expert Meeting draw on Damian Copeland, Rain Liivoja and Lauren Sanders, 'The Utility of Weapons Reviews in Addressing Concerns Raised by Autonomous Weapon Systems' (2023) 28:2 *Journal of Conflict and Security Law* 285–316 <doi.org/10.1093/jcsl/krac035>.

Case Study 1: Artificial Intelligence Target Classifier

The Artificial Intelligence Target Classifier (AITC) is a fictitious AI-enabled decision support tool designed to enhance the use of weapons by tracking, identifying and prioritising targets. The AITC analyses video footage and makes recommendations or gives warnings to military commanders to consider when planning or deciding upon an attack. The object classifier employs a convolutional neural network (CNN) programmed to recognise specific visual objects and classify them based upon indicia relevant to categories of persons and objects on the battlefield. For example, the classifier can identify an individual in a pre-determined geographic area, carrying a recognised weapon, wearing military disruptive pattern uniform and not possessing any distinctive protective emblem as an enemy combatant with a high degree of certainty (95%). The classifier is in its early stages of study and development by a private company with military funding.

Discussion questions

1. Is the AITC a 'new weapon, means or method of warfare'? Consider what criteria could be used for determining whether the capability, including any modification, should be subject to a legal review.
2. How would you go about reviewing the legality of the AITC? Consider when the legal review should commence, who should be involved in the legal review, what information the legal reviewer(s) would need, and what criteria (legal or other) would need to be considered.
3. What do you anticipate would be the outcome of the legal review? If you anticipate that the legal review would conclude that the capability is lawful, then consider what, if any, limitations or caveats might a legal review recommend.
4. How would you use the outcomes of the legal review of the AITC? Consider whether and how the outcomes of the legal review should be communicated to others who need to know about them.

Case Study 2: Autonomous Aerial Platform

This fictitious scenario deals with the reviewing State purchasing an AWS Loiterer from an allied State. The Loiterer is an aerial platform designed to, once launched, fly along a pre-designated flight path for up to six hours and target military objectives employing specific communications systems. It is equipped with sensitive radio frequency receivers that can detect and locate radio signals from radio equipment used in military headquarters and command vehicles. Operators can program the Loiterer to fly up to 3000 m in altitude and search within a designated geographic area for military objectives emitting the target radio frequencies.

Once a radio signal is identified, the Loiterer flies a specific path to triangulate the source of the radio signal and pinpoint its location. The platform carries two 50 gramme high explosive glide drones, which can be launched up to 2 km from the intended target. Once the target location is pinpointed, the platform passes the target information to one or both glide drones which are released and glide, undetected, to strike the target. Once the Loiterer launches the glide drones, the targeting process is fully autonomous. The Loiterer is programmed to return to a specified landing point on demand or when its fuel supply is low.

The normal or expected use of the Loiterer is the kinetic targeting of military objectives, including military headquarters. Testing has demonstrated that the glide drones strike their designed targets with 98% accuracy. While the 50 gramme payload has a lethal weapons effect radius of 10 m, it can cause collateral damage within 50 m of its point of impact. A human controller can monitor the Loiterer mission and, where necessary, cancel or suspend an attack. If directed, such as if there is a low risk of collateral damage assessed by the human controller, or if communications between the platform and its controller are unavailable, the Loiterer can operate autonomously once launched.

Discussion questions

1. Is the AWS Loiterer a 'new weapon, means or method of warfare'? Consider what criteria could be used for determining whether the capability, including any modification, should be subject to a legal review.
2. How would you go about reviewing the legality of the AWS Loiterer? Consider when the legal review should commence, who should be involved in the legal review, what information the legal reviewer(s) would need, and what criteria (legal or other) would need to be considered.
3. What do you anticipate would be the outcome of the legal review? If you anticipate that the legal review would conclude that the capability is lawful, then consider what, if any, limitations or caveats might a legal review recommend.
4. How would you use the outcomes of the legal review of the AWS Loiterer? Consider whether and how the outcomes of the legal review should be communicated to others who need to know about them.

Case Study 3: Uncrewed Armed Reconnaissance Vehicle

The fictional Uncrewed Armed Reconnaissance Vehicle (UARV) is a modified armed vehicle designed to conduct autonomous long-range reconnaissance and surveillance operations with a conventional heavy calibre machine gun mounted on its weapon station. The machine gun is intended primarily for defensive use, although the UARV may be authorised to attack pre-designated targets. The heavy machine gun was introduced into service in 2009 and a legal review completed prior to this. The machine gun fires 0.50 calibre (12.7mm) rounds to a distance of 4000 m from a remotely operated weapon station with an accuracy of 3–5 m at the maximum effective range.

The modified armed vehicle has not previously been considered by a legal review as it was an unarmed reconnaissance vehicle that did not fall within the reviewing State's definition of a 'new weapon, means or method of warfare'. In addition to mounting the machine gun to this platform, modifications include an AI operating system that enables its mission profile to be programmed (for example, reconnaissance within defined geographic bounds). The AI determines how it will undertake its mission based on pre-programmed tactics, techniques and procedures, environmental conditions and operational information such as known enemy locations. The armed vehicle has video, infra-red and thermal cameras to provide its operating system with environmental data. The system can classify hundreds of objects, including all known enemy tracked and wheeled vehicles, and can identify known combatants' camouflage uniforms. Military commanders can monitor the location, imagery and actions of the UARV and provide additional directions, including suspending or restricting its operations, via secure satellite communications.

Discussion questions

1. Is the UARV a 'new weapon, means or method of warfare'? Consider what criteria could be used for determining whether the capability, including any modification, should be subject to a legal review.
2. How would you go about reviewing the legality of the modified UARV? Consider when the legal review should commence, who should be involved in the legal review, what information the legal reviewer(s) would need, and what criteria (legal or other) would need to be considered.
3. What do you anticipate would be the outcome of the legal review? If you anticipate that the legal review would conclude that the capability is lawful, then consider what, if any, limitations or caveats might a legal review recommend.
4. How would you use the outcomes of the legal review of the UARV?

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Ms Navina Vijaysegaran	International Law and Security Section, Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade	Australia
Dr Pontus Winther	Department for Defence Analysis, Swedish Defence Research Agency	Sweden
Mr Renato Wolf	School of Law, University of Queensland	Australia

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